

Ophthalmic Manifestation of Methicillin Resistant Staphylococcus Aureus (MRSA) In a Tertiary Care Center, Patna, Bihar, IndiaArchana¹, Raj Nath Singh², Vijay Kumar³¹Senior Resident, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India²MBBS, MD (Ophthalmology)³Professor & Head, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Objectives:** The present study was to evaluate and compare the Ophthalmic manifestations of patients between methicillin resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) and methicillin sensitive Staphylococcus aureus (MSSA) in a tertiary care center, Patna, Bihar, India.**Methods:** We determined susceptibility of the isolates to seven antibiotics (oxacillin, penicillin, erythromycin, clindamycin, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole, vancomycin and teicoplanin) using the disc diffusion method according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standard Institute (CLSI) standards for antimicrobial susceptibility testing. We used oxacillin to test for b-lactam antibiotic resistance. We reviewed patient charts to collect demographic and clinical information.**Results:** Health exposure for ocular infection in MRSA patients was 11(36.66%) and in MSSA was 8(22.85%). It was not significant differences (p=0.22). Clinical Diagnoses Associated with Ocular MRSA and MSSA ocular had Keratitis 12(40%) and 15(42.85%) respectively, which was not significant differences (p=0.817). Conjunctivitis, lacrimal system disorder, wound infection, endophthalmitis, vision threatening disorder and others in MRSA and MSSA patients was not significant differences (p>0.05). But the lid disorder in MRSA and MSSA patients was significant differences (p=0.033). Erythromycin and clindamycin in MRSA and MSSA patient were highly significant differences (p=<0.0001). Penicillin and Sulfamethoxazole/Trimethoprim in MRSA and MSSA was significantly differences (p=0.057). MRSA was significantly more resistant than MSSA to several antibiotics including erythromycin, clindamycin, penicillin and sulfamethoxazole/trimethoprim. 83.33% of MRSA isolates were susceptible to sulfamethoxazole/trimethoprim.**Conclusions:** All MRSA isolates are susceptible to vancomycin and teicoplanin. MRSA is common in ocular Staphylococcus aureus infection in our tertiary care centre. Hence, Infectious diseases may differ by regions in epidemiologic patterns, spectrum and severity of disease, and profiles of antibiotic susceptibility.**Key words:** Ophthalmic manifestation, MRSA, MSSA.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Staphylococcus aureus (SA) is a pertinent cause of common presentations to eye infection. Staphylococcus aureus is a leading cause of ocular infections include conjunctivitis, keratitis and endophthalmitis [1,2]. Traditionally, methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus (MRSA) was almost exclusively associated with hospitals or hospital associated healthcare facilities, but its prevalence has increased in otherwise healthy patients without identifiable risk factors, such as admission to a hospital, intravenous drug use, or prior antibiotic exposure [3, 4].

In any infection, identification of causative pathogens and determination of their antibiotic resistance profiles should ideally precede initiation of antibiotic therapy [5]. Although cultures are performed for vision-threatening ocular infections,

they are seldom performed for routine eye infections, with physicians favouring empirical therapy to avoid treatment delays associated with the time required to obtain culture and sensitivity results and/or to avoid the costs of culturing [6,7]. In the absence of culture and sensitivity results, antibiotic resistance data from surveillance studies can inform the choice of initial or empirical treatment. However, regardless of how the treatment decision is made, antibiotic resistance remains an important consideration in the treatment of eye infections. The Ocular Tracking Resistance in US Today (Ocular TRUST) study [10,8, 9] was a nationwide surveillance program conducted from 2005 to 2008 to monitor antibiotic resistance specific to common ocular pathogens. Results showed high levels of methicillin resistance among staphylococci, with a

predominance of concurrent resistance to other antibiotic classes. The Antibiotic Resistance Monitoring in Ocular Microorganisms (ARMOR) study is a multicenter, nationwide, prospective surveillance study initiated in 2009 [11] and designed to extend on the Ocular TRUST study in surveying antibacterial resistance among clinically relevant isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus*, coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS), *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Haemophilus influenzae*. Objectives of our study was to evaluate and compare the ophthalmic manifestation between the patients with methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and methicillin sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA) in a tertiary care center, Patna, Bihar, India.

Material & Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of Microbiology with the collaboration of Department of Ophthalmology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar during a period from October 2023 to January 2024.

Data was collected with irrespective of age and sex. A total of 65 diagnosed cases of ocular infection patients were enrolled in the present study.

From the microbiologic laboratory database, we identified all the patients with an ocular specimen, collected by ophthalmologists, sent for bacterial culture and positive for *S. aureus*. We included no more than one isolate per patient. We determined susceptibility of the isolates to seven antibiotics (oxacillin, penicillin, erythromycin, clindamycin, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole, vancomycin and teicoplanin) using the disc diffusion method according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standard Institute (CLSI) standards for antimicrobial susceptibility testing. We used oxacillin to test for β -lactam antibiotic resistance. We reviewed patient charts to collect demographic and clinical information. Based on the structures involved, we

classified ocular infections into one of seven diagnoses: conjunctivitis, keratitis, lid disorder, lacrimal system disorder, wound infection, endophthalmitis and other (e.g., blebitis, buckle or implant infection and sclera ulcer). If the chart showed more than one diagnosis, we chose the primary pathology or the more severe diagnosis. If the patients had either: (1) a MRSA infection identified after 48 hours of admission to a hospital; (2) a history of hospitalization, surgery, dialysis, or residence in a long-term care facility within six months of the MRSA culture date; (3) a permanent indwelling catheter or percutaneous medical device present at the time of culture; or (4) a known positive culture for MRSA prior to the study period, they were thought to have healthcare exposure [12].

Statistical Analysis

Data was analysed with the help of SPSS software. Mean and standard deviations were calculated. P-value was taken less than or equal to 0.05 for significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$).

Observations & Results

Staphylococcus aureus was isolated from 65 patients. Among them, 30 were MRSA and 35 were MSSA. Rate of prevalence of MRSA was 46.15%. Mean age of ocular MRSA was 42.54 ± 28.23 years. And the mean age of ocular MSSA infection was 34.78 ± 26.54 years. It was not significant differences ($p=0.258$). In the MRSA, 18 cases were females and 12 cases were males. In MSSA, 14 cases were females and 21 cases were males. There was laterality similar eye involvement in MRSA and MSSA patients. In MRSA patients, eye involvement was right: 17, left: 9 and bilateral :7. In MSSA patients, eye involvement was right: 19, left: 11 and bilateral: 5. Health exposure for ocular infection in MRSA patients was 11(36.66%) and in MSSA was 8(22.85%). It was not significant differences ($p=0.22$). Patients with MRSA was not differed significantly from MSSA patients in the presence of underlying comorbidities ($p=0.133$).

Table 1: Comparison of demographic profile of ocular infection in MRSA and MSSA patients.

Variables	MRSA (N=30)	MSSA (35)	p-value
Age	42.54 \pm 28.23	34.78 \pm 26.54	0.258
Health exposure	11(36.66%)	8(22.85%)	0.22
Comorbidities	10(33.33%)	6(17.14%)	0.133

In the present study, there was no change in other demographics of both MRSA and MSSA groups between the study periods. Clinical Diagnoses Associated with Ocular MRSA and MSSA ocular had Keratitis 12(40%) and 15(42.85%) respectively, which was not significant differences ($p=0.817$).

Conjunctivitis, lacrimal system disorder, wound infection, endophthalmitis, vision threatening disorder and others in MRSA and MSSA patients was not significant differences ($p > 0.05$). But the lid disorder in MRSA and MSSA patients was significant differences ($p=0.033$).

Table 2: Comparison of clinical diagnoses associated with ocular MRSA and MSSA patients.

Diagnosis	MRSA (N=30)	MSSA (N=35)	P-value
Keratitis	12(40%)	15(42.85%)	0.817
Lid disorder	10(33.33%)	4(11.42%)	0.033
Conjunctivitis	7(23.33%)	8(22.85%)	0.963
Lacrimal system disorder	5(16.67%)	7(20%)	0.732
Wound infection	2(6.67%)	1(2.85%)	0.467
Endophthalmitis	2(6.67%)	1(2.85%)	0.467
Vision-threatening disorder	14(46.67%)	18(51.43%)	0.704
Others	1(3.33%)	2(5.71%)	0.650

In the present study, table 3 shows the antibiotic susceptibility in MRSA and MSSA group patients. Erythromycin and clindamycin in MRSA and MSSA patient were highly significant differences ($p < 0.0001$). Penicillin and Sulfamethoxazole/Trimethoprim in MRSA and MSSA was significantly differences ($p = 0.057$).

MRSA was significantly more resistant than MSSA to several antibiotics including erythromycin, clindamycin, penicillin and sulfamethoxazole/trimethoprim. 83.33% of MRSA isolates were susceptible to sulfamethoxazole/trimethoprim. All MRSA and MSSA isolates were susceptible to vancomycin and teicoplanin.

Table 3: Antibiotic susceptibility of MRSA and 245 MSSA for ocular infections.

Antibiotics	MRSA (N=30)	MSSA (N=35)	P-value
Erythromycin	2(6.67%)	24(68.57%)	<0.0001
Clindamycin	3(10%)	26(74.29%)	<0.0001
Penicillin	0(0)	4(11.43%)	0.057
Vancomycin	30(100%)	35(100%)	-
Teicoplanin	30(100%)	35(100%)	-
Sulfamethoxazole/Trimethoprim	25(83.33%)	34(97.14%)	0.057

Discussions

MRSA is a common cause of hospital-acquired infections [13]. Now more than half of all skin and soft tissue infections worldwide are due to the community-acquired MRSA strain [14,15]. Ocular MRSA infections can be aggressive and cause severe ophthalmic disease including blindness [16]. Frequently inadequate antibiotic coverage is prescribed for ophthalmic MRSA infections due to unfamiliarity with both the presentation of these infections and with appropriate antibiotic coverage [2]. Resistance among ocular pathogens is increasing in parallel with the increase among systemic pathogens [17,18]. Data on MRSA antibiotic sensitivity solely from ophthalmic sources has generally been limited to reports from single institutions and retrospective case series [19,20,18]. However, recent antibiograms from the US and abroad showed that CA-MRSA strains tended to be susceptible to a wide range of non-beta-lactam antibiotics [21,22].

In the present study, rate of prevalence of MRSA was 46.12%. Increasing prevalence of MRSA ophthalmic infections has been much ballyhooed in both the peer-reviewed ophthalmology as well as the non-peer-reviewed ophthalmology "throwaways". Asbell et al. [17] reported increasing prevalence of multi-drug-resistant MRSA in serious ocular infections based on the rate of increase in a national surveillance program monitoring evolving patterns

of antimicrobial susceptibility for pathogens requiring diagnostic testing. The Surveillance Network (TSN) retrieved data from over 580,000 isolates of *S. aureus* from 2000 to 2005 and found methicillin resistance increased in *S. aureus* isolates regardless of specimen source. The MRSA prevalence rate increased 12.1% during the 5-year period (from 29.5% in 2000 to 41.6% in 2005) [23].

In the present study, greater number of the patients with MRSA ocular infections had healthcare exposure than those with MSSA ocular infections. However, it is noteworthy that two thirds of the patients (19/30, 63.33%) with MRSA ocular infections had no healthcare exposure, which meant the isolates were potentially community associated. MRSA was once associated with healthcare facilities, but more recent reports showed an increasing frequency of isolates from community associated MRSA infections [24, 25]. Since most ophthalmologic patients are seen and treated as outpatients instead of inpatients, community-associated MRSA may play an important role in MRSA ocular infections.

In the present study, the most common presentation of ocular MRSA infections was keratitis (40%), followed by lid disorder (33.33%) and conjunctivitis (23.33%). And 46.67% patients of ocular MRSA infections were vision-threatening. However, previous large case series studies showed that the most common manifestation of ophthalmic MRSA

infection was conjunctivitis [8,10] or lid disorder [9]; vision-threatening infections were relatively uncommon [26, 1]. Our results may have differed due to selection bias, because there were more severe cases in our hospital. Also, physicians may differ in which cases they sent for diagnostic testing; some may tend to culture only the most serious cases. Third, we may exclude some patients with ocular infections, while the cultures were not done by ophthalmologists. MRSA is believed to cause a more severe disease than MSSA, but this observation has not reached consensus [27]. Our results were not shown that MRSA caused more severe ocular diseases than MSSA; this agrees with Freidlin's study, which reported MRSA and MSSA caused similar eye disease [1]. We were found that patients with MRSA were more likely to have lid infections. In addition, the rate of lid disorder caused by MRSA significantly increased. Community associated MRSA has a reported predilection for causing skin and soft tissue infections [12,29]. And we were also found that lid and lacrimal system disorders were more common, but keratitis, endophthalmitis and wound infection were less common among community associated MRSA cases than healthcare associated MRSA cases [30]. Thus, 63.33% of patients with MRSA ocular infections were community-associated and the paralleled significant increase in the rate of the MRSA patients without healthcare exposure (i.e. community-associated MRSA).

According to antibiotic susceptibility profiles, vancomycin and teicoplanin were the most active agent against ocular MRSA isolates, whereas sulfamethoxazole/trimethoprim retained some degree of activity against MRSA, but was less effective than in previous studies [2, 1]. Although vancomycin retains extremely high efficacy against MRSA, *S. aureus* with reduced susceptibility to vancomycin was identified [31]. Since prior vancomycin use is a risk factor for MRSA with reduced vancomycin susceptibility [32] and no convincing evidence shows that routine vancomycin prophylaxis is effective in elective cataract surgery [33]. We recommend that ophthalmologists follow guideline of the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [34] and the American Academy of Ophthalmology [36] against the routine use of vancomycin for prophylaxis to halt the spread of resistance. Several recent studies have reported that MRSA has a high rate of in vitro resistance to fluoroquinolones, including new generation ones, the most popular empiric therapy in ocular infections [2,1,10,36,37,38]. We were not tested fluoroquinolones in our study because they were not included in the recommended list of antibiotics published by the CLSI. In Taiwan, National data from 2000 (TSAR program) has demonstrated 40% *S. aureus* (including MSSA and MRSA) in vitro resistance to ciprofloxacin [39]. We may extend the

antibiotic susceptibility profiles to include commonly used topical antibiotics in future studies.

Conclusions

The present study concluded that the all-MRSA isolates are susceptible to vancomycin and teicoplanin. MRSA is common in ocular *Staphylococcus aureus* infection in our tertiary care centre. Hence, Infectious diseases may differ by regions in epidemiologic patterns, spectrum and severity of disease, and profiles of antibiotic susceptibility.

References

1. Freidlin J, Acharya N, Lietman TM, Cevallos V, et al. Spectrum of eye disease caused by methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Am J Ophthalmol*. 2007; 144:313–31.
2. Blomquist P, et al. Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* infections of the eye and orbit. *Trans Am Ophthalmol Soc*. 2006; 104:322–45.
3. Warshawsky B, Hussain Z, Gregson DB, et al. Hospital and community-based surveillance of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*: previous hospitalization is the major risk factor. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiol*. 2000; 221: 724–7.
4. Herold BC, Immergluck LC, Maranan MC, et al. Community acquired methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in children with no identified predisposing risk. *JAMA*. 1998; 279:593–8.
5. Goff DA, Jankowski C, Tenover FC. Using rapid diagnostic tests to optimize antimicrobial selection in antimicrobial stewardship programs. *Pharmacotherapy*. 2012;32(8):677–68 7
6. American Academy of Ophthalmology. Bacterial keratitis preferred practice pattern–2018. <https://www.aao.org/preferred-practice-pattern/bacterial-keratitis-ppp-2018>. Published November 2018. Accessed March 5, 2019.
7. American Academy of Ophthalmology. Conjunctivitis preferred practice pattern–2018. <https://www.aao.org/preferred-practice-pattern/conjunctivitis-ppp-2018>. Published November 2018. Accessed March 5, 2019.
8. Asbell PA, Sahn DF. Longitudinal nationwide antimicrobial susceptibility surveillance in ocular isolates: results from Ocular TRUST 2. Presented at: American Society of Cataract and Refractive Surgery Annual Meeting; April 28, 2008; San Diego, CA.
9. Asbell PA, Sahn DF, Shedden A. Ocular TRUST 3: ongoing longitudinal surveillance of antimicrobial susceptibility in ocular isolates. Presented at: American Society of Cataract and Refractive Surgery Annual Meeting; April 7, 2009; San Francisco, CA.
10. Asbell PA, Colby KA, Deng S, et al. Ocular TRUST: nationwide antimicrobial

- susceptibility patterns in ocular isolates. *Am J Ophthalmol* 2008;145(6):951-958.
11. Haas W, Pillar CM, Torres M, Morris TW, Sahn DF. Monitoring antibiotic resistance in ocular microorganisms: results from the Antibiotic Resistance Monitoring in Ocular microorganisms (ARMOR) 2009 Surveillance Study. *Am J Ophthalmol*. 2011;152(4):567.e3 -574.e3.
 12. Naimi TS, LeDell KH, Como-Sabeti K, Borchardt SM, Boxrud DJ, et al. Comparison of community- and health care-associated methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* infection. *JAMA* 2003; 290:2976–2984.
 13. Weber, J.T. (2005) Community-associated methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Clinical Infectious Diseases* 2005; 41:S269-S272.
 14. Hersh, A.L., Chambers, H.F., Maselli, J.H. and Gonzales, R. (2008) National trends in ambulatory visits and antibiotic prescribing for skin and soft tissue infections. *Archives of Internal Medicine* 2008; 168: 1585-1591.
 15. Gardam, M.A. Is MRSA an emerging community pathogen? A review of the literature. *Canadian Journal of Infectious Diseases* 2000; 11: 202-211.
 16. Rutar, T., Chambers, H.F., Crawford, J.B., Perdreaux Remington, F., Zwick, O.M., Karr, M., Diehn, J.J. and Cockerham, K.P. Ophthalmic manifestations of infections caused by the USA300 clone of community-associated methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Ophthalmology* 2006; 113:1455-1462.
 17. Asbell PA, Sahn DF, Shaw D, et al. Increasing prevalence of methicillin resistance in serious ocular infections caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* in the United States: 2000–2005. *J Cataract Refract Surg*. 2008; 34:814–8.
 18. Hořding G. Acute bacterial conjunctivitis. *Acta Ophthalmol (Oxf)*. 2008; 86:5–17.
 19. Rudd JC, Moshirfar M. Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* keratitis after laser in situ keratomileusis. *J Cataract Refract Surg*. 2001; 27(3):471–3.
 20. Karth PA, Karth JW. Endophthalmitis following photorefractive keratectomy with a history of radial keratotomies: a case report. *J Ophthalmic Inflamm Infect*. 2013; 11:1186–9.
 21. Amato M, Pershing S, Walvick M, et al. Trends in ophthalmic manifestations of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) in a northern California pediatric population. *J AAPOS*. 2013; 17:243–7.
 22. Mantadakis E, Maraki S, Michailidis L, et al. Antimicrobial susceptibility of Gram-positive cocci isolated from patients with conjunctivitis and keratitis in Crete, Greece. *J Microbiol Immunol Infect*. 2013; 46:41–7.
 23. Sahn D, Marsilio MK, Piazza G. Antimicrobial resistance in key bloodstream bacterial isolates: electronic surveillance with the Surveillance Network Database-USA. *Clin Infect Dis*. 1999; 29:259–63.
 24. Chambers HF (2001) The changing epidemiology of *Staphylococcus aureus*? *Emerg Infect Dis* 7: 178–182.
 25. Wang JL, Chen SY, Wang JT, Wu GH, Chiang WC, et al. (2008) Comparison of both clinical features and mortality risk associated with bacteremia due to community-acquired methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* and methicillin-susceptible *S. aureus*. *Clin Infect Dis* 2008; 46: 799–806.
 26. Shanmuganathan VA, Armstrong M, Buller A, Tullo AB. External ocular infections due to methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). *Eye* 2005; 19: 284–291.
 27. Cosgrove SE, Sakoulas G, Perencevich EN, Schwaber MJ, Karchmer AW, et al. Comparison of mortality associated with methicillin-resistant and methicillin-susceptible *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteremia: a meta-analysis. *Clin Infect Dis* 2003; 36: 53–59.
 28. Melzer M, Eykyn SJ, Gransden WR, Chinn S. Is methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* more virulent than methicillin-susceptible *S. aureus*? A comparative cohort study of British patients with nosocomial infection and bacteremia. *Clin Infect Dis* 2003; 37: 1453–1460.
 29. Skiest DJ, Brown K, Cooper TW, Hoffman-Roberts H, Mussa HR, et al. Prospective comparison of methicillin-susceptible and methicillin-resistant community-associated *Staphylococcus aureus* infections in hospitalized patients. *J Infect* 54: 427–434.
 30. Hsiao CH, Chuang CC, Tan HY, Ma DH, Lin KK, et al. Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* Ocular Infection: A 10-Year Hospital-Based Study. *Ophthalmology* 2012; 119: 522–527.
 31. Hawser SP, Bouchillon SK, Hoban DJ, Dowzicky M, Babinchak T. Rising incidence of *Staphylococcus aureus* with reduced susceptibility to vancomycin and susceptibility to antibiotics: a global analysis 2004–2009. *Int J Antimicrob Agents* 2007; 37: 219–224.
 32. Fridkin SK, Hageman J, McDougal LK, Mohammed J, Jarvis WR, et al. Epidemiological and microbiological characterization of infections caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* with reduced susceptibility to vancomycin, United States, 1997–2001. *Clin Infect Dis* 2003; 36: 429–439.

33. Gordon YJ. Vancomycin prophylaxis and emerging resistance: are ophthalmologists the villains? The heroes? *Am J Ophthalmol* 2001; 131: 371–376.
34. Recommendations for preventing spread of vancomycin resistance. *Am J Health Syst Pharm* 1995; 52: 1272–1274.
35. Force A-CT. The prophylactic use of vancomycin for intraocular surgery. *Quality of Care Publications*, Number 515, American Academy of Ophthalmology, San Francisco, CA, October 1999.
36. Asbell PA, Sahm DF, Shaw M, Draghi DC, Brown NP. Increasing prevalence of methicillin resistance in serious ocular infections caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* in the United States: 2000 to 2005. *J Cataract Refract Surg* 2008; 34: 814–818.
37. Major JC Jr, Engelbert M, Flynn HW Jr, Miller D, Smiddy WE, et al. *Staphylococcus aureus* endophthalmitis: antibiotic susceptibilities, methicillin resistance, and clinical outcomes. *Am J Ophthalmol* 2010; 149: 278–283 e271.
38. Marangon FB, Miller D, Muallem MS, Romano AC, Alfonso EC. Ciprofloxacin and levofloxacin resistance among methicillin-sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates from keratitis and conjunctivitis. *American Journal of Ophthalmology* 2004; 137: 453–458.
39. McDonald LC, Lauderdale TL, Shiau YR, Chen PC, Lai JF, et al. The status of antimicrobial resistance in Taiwan among Gram-positive pathogens: the Taiwan Surveillance of Antimicrobial Resistance (TSAR) programme, 2000. *Int J Antimicrob Agents* 2004; 23: 362–370.